

An Academic Review on How Important the Socio -Economic Criteria of Countries in Granting Citizenship

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Abstract

Naturalization rates among established immigrants throughout Europe remain low and vary greatly (OECD/EU 2018), even though citizenship regulations are a vital indication of a country's overall approach to the incorporation of immigrants (Huddleston and Vink 2015). The average for the European Union is 59%, which is lower than the norms for the United States (62%) and Australia (81%), as well as Canada (90%). When politicians and scholars attempt to explain variances in the naturalization process from one nation to another, they often allude to variations in citizenship legislation and the make-up of the immigrant population (Brubaker 1992; Joppke 2007; Goodman 2010). In debates on naturalization, the major focus is on the well-researched grounds and laws for citizenship. Frequently, an emphasis is placed on the legal requirements for naturalization via the usual procedure. In spite of this, there seems to be an "implementation gap" throughout Europe when one considers the citizenship laws, naturalization procedures, and the number of persons who have been naturalized. If the requirements, sensitivities, and standards that we have stated above are adhered to, citizenship based on money or investment may also be helpful. It is recommended that, as an alternative to outright turning down the application, the application be reviewed to determine how it should be managed. In recent times, some new regulations have been made in the provisions regarding the acquisition of citizenship by exceptional means in the Turkish Citizenship Law, which is the main regulation regarding the acquisition of Turkish citizenship, and the Regulation on the implementation of this Law. In addition, the regime regarding the

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acquisition of Turkish citizenship through exceptional means has undergone a fundamental change within the framework of these regulations. For more information, see the Turkish Citizenship Law and the Regulation on the implementation of this Law. [The Law Governing Citizenship in Turkey]. In this context, the nature and scope of the regulations regarding the exceptional acquisition of citizenship in Turkish law should be managed from the perspective of historical research. Additionally, the nature and scope of the regulations in other laws regarding the exceptional acquisition of citizenship should be investigated in detail. The pertinent regulation of Turkish Citizenship Law No. 5901, which contains the regulation addressing the acquisition of Turkish citizenship as an exception in Turkish law, is essential in terms of the scope both before to and after the modification made with Law No. 6735. This is because the relevant regulation includes the regulation regarding the acquisition of Turkish citizenship as an exception in Turkish law.

Keywords: *Granting Citizenship by Countries, Dual Citizenship, Citizenship Criteria, Socio - economic Criteria for Citizenship Applications*

Introduction

The purpose of conducting this study for Turkey is to establish whether or not the modification will have an effect on the applicable rule. In accordance with the provisions of Article 6 of this law, and by making a specific reference to the provision in the text of the article that permits a person to acquire Turkish citizenship after residing in Turkey for a certain amount of time, which is generally considered to be a method of naturalization, the exception is granted in the article that came before it today. Naturalization is a possibility for people.

It is not necessary for a person to have been in Turkey for five years before to the application date and to have proven by his or her conduct that he or she has chosen to dwell in Turkey in order for them to be eligible for exceptional naturalization in accordance with the aforementioned article. This applies to a person who can be exceptionally naturalized.

This was done to facilitate the comparatively easy acquisition of Turkish citizenship for a certain group of individuals. Article 6 of the Law, which controls the method of general (ordinary) citizenship, contains a list of the seven subparagraphs that make up the requirements that must be

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met in order to acquire Turkish citizenship by the general route. To put it another way, it is obvious that the qualifications connected to reaching the age of majority (adulthood), having strong morals, being in good health, being able to speak Turkish, and having a source of income are also required. The relevant articles of both statutes are constructed in such a manner that the exception to these provisions are regulated by reference to the article that came before it. These are the provisions that control the method naturalization and residency (and purpose to dwell) in general. It has been determined, in some instances, that persons may be given Turkish citizenship even without submitting an application for it.

Acceptance Rules and Processes

To begin, according to Huddleston 2013, there does not seem to be any kind of consistent link between the degree of restrictiveness of ordinary naturalization requirements and the mechanisms that are used throughout Europe. When looking at the 35 nations that make up Europe, we find that half of them have laws and procedures that are restricted to varied degrees; however, certain countries (like Portugal and Sweden) make both the legislation and the procedure more accessible. There are additional nations, such as the Baltics and, to a lesser degree, France and Germany, that set limits on both the law and the procedure.

To put it another way, concentrating just on legal criteria does not show the nature of and the number of operational hurdles. Second, while there is a positive association between acquisition rates and nationality laws, this correlation is not as substantial as one would expect it to be. According to Huddleston and Falcke 2020, immigrants from impoverished nations tend to have a higher likelihood of acquiring citizenship in some countries with restrictive rules than in other countries with regulations that are equivalent to or even more thorough than the restrictive laws in question. The great majority of studies concentrate their attention on the completion of the naturalization procedure (that is, the naturalization rate or share), but not on the whole process of implementation. their process encompasses the several processes when immigrants begin to develop interested in citizenship, petition for citizenship, and continue until they are successful in accomplishing their goal.

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Citizenship laws are a collective name for the substantive standards that establish eligibility and conditions for the acquisition or loss of citizenship. The process of applying these criteria is broken down into a series of formal processes that are referred to as procedures. Laws pertaining to citizenship may be found in each and every nation. The implementation of citizenship regulations at each level of the naturalization process creates a new set of opportunities and obstacles that are specific to that stage. The choice to apply for citizenship as an adult immigrant is a personal one that, depending on the circumstances, may be strengthened or weakened by the surroundings. The decision to apply for citizenship is a personal one.

Naturalization is seldom an automated process for authorities, with judgments being made by a single decision maker based on solely objective requirements. Because of this, comparative international research on immigrants' goals and abilities to achieve citizenship has only been undertaken by a few number of studies. On the one hand, this scope focuses on the types of people who are most likely to obtain citizenship, and on the other hand, this scope focuses on the numerous target nations and the regulations and processes for acquiring citizenship. The analytical approach and ideas offered in this paper are supported by an investigation into two significant research voids pertaining to citizenship. These gaps include the significance of contextual factors as well as the disparity between immigrants' desire to earn citizenship and their competence to do so (Huddleston and Dag). Tjaden (2012).

Logistic Regressions

To investigate the significance of citizenship laws and procedures in connection to crucial person level and country of origin factors, logistic regressions are utilized. There are several different robustness tests, each of which is conducted using a different kind of regression analysis and a different operationalization of the key variables that are of interest. In the last section of the paper, major implications for academics and policy makers are discussed, along with a discussion of the findings considering earlier research that concentrated on a single country.

Method

Beginning with North America (Bernard 1936; Evans 1988; Yang 1994; Devoretz 2008), the factors that are very influential in deciding a person's nationality change as one moves on to other traditional destination countries and some exemplary for other countries (see overview, Liebig, and Von, Harem 2011).

Human, Social and Human Capitals

This significant transatlantic research provides more evidence that highlights the significance of crucial individual, country of origin, and destination variables in the acquisition of citizenship. It is usual practice to identify immigrants' human capital as the key factor in defining their "civil capital," which includes their capacity to seek citizenship. It is normal practice to use country-specific capital such as language competence, education, job experience, and duration of residency as examples of this kind of country-specific capital. (Bernard 1936; Evans 1988; Yang 1994; Devoretz 2008; Liebig and Von Haren 2011; Peters et al. 2018). In addition to human capital, social capital and networks are essential components in the process of developing the information and mobilization channels that immigrants often need to achieve citizenship (Bloemraad 2006a; Just and Anderson 2012; Logan et al. 2012; Abascal 2015). Altering one's motivations to participate in civic life is another impact social capital may have.

For immigrants who are married or have children, acquiring citizenship is more of a social choice than an individual decision because it enables them to extend the benefits of citizenship with only a marginal increase in related expenditures (Portes and Curtis 1987; Ivlevs and King 2012; Peters et al. 2016).

Literature Study

Increasingly, the characteristics of the migrant's country of origin are also being included in the multivariate analysis. This is done to reveal an important set of relative benefits and costs for migrants who have different return migration expectations based on the level of development in their country of origin, the geographic distance between their country and the host country, the number of refugees in the host country, and the nationality of origin. This is done in order to

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demonstrate a broad variety of relative advantages and costs for migrants who have various return migration expectations (Portes and Curtis, 1987; Yang 1994; Jones- Correa 2001; Bueker 2005; Constant et al. 2007; Mazzolari 2009; Logan et al. others 2012; Vink et al. 2013) (Portes and Curtis, 1987; Yang 1994; Jones- Correa 2001; Bueker 2005; Constant et al.

In addition to the features of the country of origin, the qualities of the country of destination emerge as some of the most important, if not the most important, determinants of citizenship acquisition. Moreover, the characteristics of the country of origin continue to play a significant role. Comparative research in Europe has made the most significant contribution to the examination of the relationships between acquisition rates and citizenship policies, which are often quantified in terms of legal requirements (Jones- Correa 2001; Bloemraad 2006b; Haney -Lopez 2006; van Hook et al. 2006; Logan et al. 2012; Fox). & Bloemraad , 2015). (Janoski 2010; Reichel 2011; Gonzalez- Ferrer and Morales 2013; Vink et al. 2013; Beine et al. 2016; Stadlmair 2017; Hansen and Clemens 2018). (“Naturalisation in context: how nationality laws and ... - Springer”)

The naturalization process is underpinned by a substantial, though often undetectable, impact exerted by the interests of immigrants. Although the fundamental aspects of citizenship have received a significant amount of attention in the scholarly literature, relatively little is known about the ways in which each of these aspects impacts the various stages of the process. The great majority of research on naturalization rates have difficulties differentiating between interest and ability. This is mostly because the data that is available is limited, and there is not enough information accessible to provide an in-depth analysis of the full citizenship process. Elements found to be connected with the process of acquiring citizenship are interpreted in connection to anticipated advantages (also known as interest) or anticipated expenses (also known as ability), or both, in the absence of this framework or these facts. In the next portion of the analytical framework, which is focused on individual-level characteristics, these interpretive challenges are dissected into the component elements that make up each of them. It would appear to be crucial to differentiate between interest and ability given the findings of the few studies that have been undertaken in a single nation. These studies have shown that the primary elements that contribute to the acquisition of citizenship are connected to interest and ability in a variety of distinct and sometimes even opposing ways.

Türkiye Example

Turkey is now hosting roughly three and a half million Syrian refugees as of the month of September 2021. Among the provinces with the biggest concentration of these refugees, the provinces of Istanbul, Gaziantep, and Hatay are some of the most notable examples. Despite the fact that more than fifty percent of the population is under the age of eighteen, fewer than two percent of the population is above the age of sixty-five. The remaining ones have the capacity to actively contribute. The fact that some Syrian refugees were able to settle in Turkey and launch businesses there has resulted in an influx of monetary resources into the Turkish economy as well as the establishment of work opportunities for a large number of individuals, including Turkish nationals. An overwhelming majority of individuals in this town (87.1%), according to a research, feel that Syrians should be denied any and all political rights. The foundation of this style of thinking in society is the notion that Syrians conduct their lives in a manner that is distinctive from the practices of other civilizations. According to the findings of the study, aspirations for citizenship among Syrians may be broken down into four distinct buckets:

1. *Persistence and trust,*
2. *rights and duties,*
3. *rational choice and*
4. *Belonging*

It has been shown that the expectations of Syrians towards citizenship are mostly centered in the areas of permanence and trust, logical choices, and rights. [Citizenship] is something that the Syrians take immense pride in. It is much simpler to understand the significance of stability for Turkey's youthful people when one considers the reality that the vast majority of Syrian refugees have families and children that they are responsible for. Başolu was able to gather data from his empirical studies that provide credence to the idea that citizenship is a suitable option for refugees. The data that was gathered out in the field provided support for these outcomes. Başolu makes it clear that the transient character of Syrians makes it difficult for them to form meaningful

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relationships in Turkey. This is based on the idea that "social cohesion" is one of the most significant issues that occur because of migration processes. According to Başolu, the idea of citizenship for refugees has ramifications that extend well beyond its standing as a legal notion.

More Laws Regulating the Process

The procedure of obtaining citizenship is being more strictly regulated with each new legislation that is enacted. They are undergoing a process of reorganization for a variety of reasons, the most prominent of which is the movement and mobility of people across international boundaries. Studies that compare different forms of citizenship make use of a variety of distinct ideas to explain the many varied policy frameworks. Arbitration, liberalization, restriction, marketization, ethnicization, and the ethnicity of citizenship are some of the topics that fall within this category. There is no denying the validity of the contention that the recent policy change in Turkey pertaining to naturalization processes must be understood in the context of wider global trends and conceptual differences.

It is necessary to first investigate the citizenship policy that has been in place ever since the republic was founded in order to acquire a deeper comprehension of the breadth of the most recent alterations. Only then will it be possible to get this comprehension. The Turkish citizenship system is characterized by a degree of selectivity that is based on a person's ethnicity and religion. This selectivity is closely tied with the foundation of the Turkish nation-state. Before the necessity of assimilation was recognized, the inclusion of non-kin was not a concern. As a result, some (Sunni) Muslim groups that could be assimilated to Turkishness only within the framework of certain historical-cultural and ideological boundaries or that were predicted to become Turkish acquired Turkish citizenship as immigrants, while other Sunni Muslim groups remained outside of it. To put it another way, the incorporation of non-related individuals was not a worry until it became clear that assimilation was essential. Second, the government has conducted research to determine the sort of shift that occurred in the exclusionary principle of the past as a result of the practices of citizenship in order to achieve its own political and economic goals, even if in some ways it does follow certain trends that are occurring all over the globe.

This policy shift, which is feasible via the systematized use of exceptional citizenship practice, has been apparent with the acquisition of Turkish citizenship by investor citizens and Syrian refugees

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picked according to their qualities. This change in policy is made possible by the systematized use of exceptional citizenship practice. Changes in policy have been implemented thanks to an organized effort to promote exemplary citizenship practices. Within the framework of this method, a restricted ethnicity aligns with class selectivity. This strategy is distinct from the techniques that have been followed regularly in the past in two different ways. Throughout the course of the history of the Republic, a new phenomenon has begun to develop. As a direct consequence of this, the present circumstance is connected with a degree of de-ethnicization, in addition to a newly developed inclusivity. The marketization that is evident in Turkey's investor citizenship program and entering the nation via the citizenship system are nonetheless clear limits of the trend toward ethnic de-identification.

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Findings

Studies concentrate on a variety of scenarios in which immigrant groups anticipate significant benefits from citizenship yet have poor acquisition rates. In the United States, among Mexicans (Portes and Curtis 1987), in Germany after the 1999 Citizenship law reform (Constant et al. 2007; Kahanec and Serkan Tosun 2009; Hochman 2011), among the Russophone minority in Latvia (Ivlevs and King 2012), and in France, among immigrants from Muslim backgrounds and disadvantaged backgrounds (Carrillo 2015), acquisition rates were lower than expected. According to Portes and Curtis (1987), there are fewer characteristics that can be used to predict interest, and those variables are seldom the same as those that can be used to predict naturalization. According to Kahanec and Serkan Tosun (2009) and Hochman (2011), the demographic traits and life experiences of immigrants who are not interested in the nation are distinct from those of

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immigrants who are interested in the country and/or have become naturalized citizens. It is possible to explain the capacity to gain citizenship using the typical individual-level factors related with naturalization rates; however, it is not always the case that these criteria can explain the motivation in doing so. Because of this, the overall acquisition rates do not adequately indicate the amount of interest that immigrants have in attaining citizenship in the United States. The outcomes of these research suggest that an individual's interest in his nation may be driven less by the individual's qualities than by the environment in which he lives. According to Hochman (2011), the process of constructing one's social identity as an immigrant includes an individual's interest in their home country as a component of a larger process.

The first scholars to discover the elements that impact immigrants' opinions on the meaning of nationality were Portes and Curtis (1987). Studies that came after this one has provided more insight on these aspects. The first and second hypotheses are based on the relative benefits that immigrants acquire and the social networks that they engage in. The first potential explanation is that immigrants are more grounded in their country of destination rather than their country of origin.

Social Capital Theory

The links that immigrants have to their place of origin, as well as the return plans and incentives that are provided by that nation, have a role in shaping their perspectives on the relative benefits and costs of attaining citizenship in the United States. The second reason, which is compatible with social capital theory and is referred to as "settlement" in the target country rather than in the country of origin, is that people go there to live. This is since family, friends, and communities of immigrants might differ in their understanding of the meaning and advantages of citizenship, as well as their plans for when they will return home. The processes that must be gone through to get citizenship are still another aspect that contributes to the decision to do so. Finally, the 'informal features' of the target nation (Hochman 2011) comprise distinct 'barriers and attitudes' (Portes and Curtis 1987) that influence immigrants' knowledge and attitudes towards the naturalization process. Some immigrants who have had negative experiences with outgroups may erroneously

believe that attaining citizenship would not provide them the advantages that were promised or the in-group recognition that was promised to them (Kahanec and Serkan Tosun 2009; Carrillo 2015).

Some academics have been inspired to investigate the significance of certain marketing methods as well as hurdles to entrance, such as fees (Felix et al. 2008; Thranhardt 2008; Logan et al. 2012; Hainmueller and Hangartner 2013; Hainmueller et al. 2018). Therefore, immigrants' views of the meaning, benefits, and costs of citizenship may be altered by citizenship procedures, a potential element that has not been examined as thoroughly as it should have been. Citizenship in the host nation provides those who were born in another country with a feeling of security in the state in which they dwell, the option to cast a ballot, and "can aid social integration, from one's health to social ties with others" (Bloemraad, 2017: 544). Research shows that naturalization of immigrants leads to increases in voter turnout (Bevelander and Pendakur , 2011), political knowledge, and a sense of political effectiveness (Hainmueller , Hangartner , and Pietrantuono , 2015) among those born outside the United States (Helgertz , Bevelander , and Tegunimataka , 2014; Peters, Vink and Schmeets , 2018; Peters, Schmeets and Vink , 2019). Citizenship in a developed and democratic nation may be a transformative experience for some immigrants (Aptekar, 2015), while for others, it may reflect more pragmatic aspirations such as improved freedom of movement. Researchers commonly correlate the different evaluations of utility of citizenship escalation with factors of origin in terms of the relative increased benefit of citizenship of destination compared to citizenship of origin (Yang, 1994). These associations are made in terms of the relative additional benefit of citizenship of destination compared to citizenship of origin.

[The Institutional Context That Determines Whether Dual Citizenship Is Possible in Countries](#)

Recent years have witnessed a rise in the number of studies that emphasize the need of include citizenship possibilities in a more comprehensive view on the life trajectories of immigrants (Hainmueller et al., 2018; Helgertz and Bevelander, 2017; Peters, Vink, and Schmeets, 2016). Additionally, the institutional context that determines whether or not dual citizenship is possible in the countries of origin (Jones- Correa, 2001), the requirements for obtaining citizenship in the target countries (Bloemraad, 2006), and the interaction between these factors all have an impact (Vink, Prokic-Breuer, and Dronkers), 2013. Because of this, the present study helps us understand why naturalization rates range dramatically amongst distinct groups of immigrants in single

destination nations. These differences are dependent on the characteristics of the immigrants' countries of origin, the paths their lives have taken, and their socioeconomic standing. The great majority of research, on the other hand, investigate the naturalization of immigrants solely in the setting of a particular destination country. As a consequence of this, these research either concentrate individual level and country-of-origin variation or focus on groups of origin identified in numerous comparative studies (for example, Bloemraad et al., 2006; Yasenov et al., 2019). Both of these approaches have their advantages and disadvantages.

They do not make it any simpler to comprehend disparate results in destination settings, such as those on the significance of schooling (Bueker, 2005: 110; Yang, 1994: 468). –489) or dual citizenship (Helgertz and Bevelander , 2017: 685–688; Peters, Vink , and Schmeets , 2016: 368). In addition, recent international comparisons of naturalization rates considering the institutional setting (Huddleston and Falcke, 2020; Vink, Prokic-Breuer, and Dronkers, 2013) investigate the long-term variability in the naturalization of immigrants in the context of variations in citizenship policy.

This is because cross-sectional data does not allow the collection of longitudinal information.

- (i) *National citizenship of these highly developed countries with long migration experiences generally comes with a similar package of social and political rights and provides access to mobility rights within the EU;*
- (ii) *citizenship requirements vary between countries and over time in two of the most controversial aspects: civil integration requirements and the admissibility of dual citizenship; And*
- (iii) *long -term migration experience generally provides income and access with a similar package of social and political rights.*

Using data from population registries, it is also crucial to consider the factors that are connected with these disparities. In order to establish how cumulative naturalization rates, change across

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immigrant groups in response to changing institutional circumstances, it is appropriate to apply harmonized versions of the Cox proportional hazards model in a number of distinct subsample studies. The idea of citizenship is essential to the functioning of nations on a global scale as an organizational principle. States determine who among their populations belong to those whom they control and for whom they accept responsibility to other states by establishing laws on citizenship and voting rights. These laws may be found in state constitutions.

The rules that govern the process of becoming a naturalized citizen, as well as the processes for getting citizenship at birth, vary greatly from one nation to the next. The great majority of countries around the globe now acknowledge the legality of dual citizenship, which may be held by immigrants, immigrants, or both immigrants and immigrants. It is standard practice to provide non-citizens of a country the right to vote in national, supranational, and even local elections in the country in which they live, notably in Europe and South America. This right to vote may extend down to the level of the individual municipality. However, out of all the countries in the world, only five of them allow their people to vote in national elections, regardless of whether or not they are citizens of the country, and none of these countries let their residents run for office.

The Concept of Statelessness

If a person does not have a nationality, it might be challenging for them to attend school, go to the doctor, obtain a job, create a bank account, or even get married. These activities can be prohibitively tough. Due to the fact that they do not have a nationality, these things may be challenging for them. This predicament affects the lives of millions of people all over the globe, and such individuals are referred to as "stateless." In accordance with the United Nations Convention on the Status of Stateless Persons, a stateless person is defined as "any person who is not recognized as a national by any State under the operation of its law." There is no way to know the precise number of persons who do not have nationality or passports, but the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR) estimates that there are at least 12 million across the globe.

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In addition to the fact that stateless people regularly have their citizenship rights infringed, a variety of other breaches of human rights are routinely committed against them as well. They may have a difficult time exercising their fundamental rights, such as the right to labor, education, and health, as well as the freedom to travel. If a person is born in the territory of a state or is the child of a citizen of that state and the person's mother or father is not a citizen of that state, then the person is regarded to have been born in the territory of that state and is entitled to nationality according to the state. This is the case even if the person's mother or father is not a citizen of that state. When a person's citizenship is revoked or lost, the state is obligated to take steps to ensure that individual citizens are not rendered stateless as a result of these events. Discrimination, which can be based on a variety of factors, such as minority status, religion or belief, age, gender identity or gender expression, disability, language, racial or ethnic origin, gender, gender characteristics, or sexual orientation — or a combination of these factors — is one of the leading causes of statelessness. When we talk about the political aspect of citizenship, we mean the rights and obligations that come with being a citizen of a country. Statelessness is one of the leading causes of statelessness. It is expected that acquaintance with the political system, as well as the cultivation of democratic attitudes and participation abilities, will lead to the expansion of this component. The social component of citizenship refers to the manner in which members of a community interact with one another and calls for a particular level of commitment and solidarity from its members. It is required to possess both social skills and an awareness of the social connections that are present in the society in order to develop this component. This understanding of the social ties that are present in the society is necessary. The "cultural component" of citizenship refers to the awareness of a common cultural past, and it is this awareness that is supposed to be alluded to by the term. The cultural aspect needs to be fostered via an individual's acquaintance with history and fundamental abilities (language competency, reading, and writing), in addition to an individual's cultural background. The economic facet of citizenship seeks to provide a representation of the dynamic relationship that occurs between a person and the consumer and labor marketplaces in which they participate. It incorporates the right to labor in addition to the fundamental right to a means of subsistence.

Economy

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In order to fully realize this dimension, economics, both in the sense of labor and in the sense of other economic activities, as well as skills connected to vocational education and training, play an essential role. Participating in the many socialization processes that take place in diverse contexts such as schools, families, civic organizations, political parties, and peer groups, in addition to associations, mass media, and neighborhoods, is one way to accomplish these four facets of citizenship. These facets of citizenship may be completed by a person who is a good citizen. If this is not the case, then full citizenship will never be attained because it will be precarious, much like the legs of a chair. Each person must be able to operate all four dimensions in an equal and balanced manner with the others, otherwise full citizenship will never be attained.

What Kind of Relationships Are There With Other People That Make You Feel Like You Belong?

When we are a part of a community, it is essential that we have the capacity to have an effect on the community, take part in the evolution of the community, and make a contribution that is beneficial to the community's health and happiness as a whole. As a consequence of this, citizenship may also be seen of as a practice, namely the habit of taking an active role in the operations of our society. This kind of interaction may take place in our local neighborhood, in a social organization that is either official or informal, in our country, or even across the whole world.

The idea of "active citizenship" refers to the practice of contributing to the growth of one's community by taking part in endeavors that attempt to improve the quality of life for all individuals who are already a member of that community. Democratic citizenship is a closely similar term that highlights the conviction that citizenship ought to be based on democratic principles and values such as pluralism, respect for human dignity, and the rule of law. Democratic citizenship is a belief that citizenship ought to be founded on democratic principles and values. A view that democratic principles and ideals ought to form the basis for citizenship is what we mean when we talk about democratic citizenship.

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Participation, respect for human rights, and citizenship are three crucial aspects of citizenship. Everyone has both the right and the duty to freely participate in the cultural life of the society, to appreciate the arts, and to enjoy the benefits of the advancement and development of science. The right to citizenship has been reinforced in several new international agreements, one of which being the European Convention on Citizenship (1997) that was established by the Council of Europe. When addressing internationally recognized norms, the words "nationality" and "citizenship" are often believed to be identical with one another. The right to one's nationality is of the utmost significance because of the bearing it has on the day-to-day actions of individuals in each country. Being a recognized citizen of a country confers a number of rights, some of which include the right to vote, the right to hold public office, the right to social security, the right to benefit from health services, the right to public education, the right of permanent residence, the right to own land, and, depending on the country, the right to paid employment. In this regard, subarticles include the rights to vote and hold public office. Although every country has the power to define its own citizens and citizens as well as the rights and obligations that come with these identities, international human rights agreements set some constraints on state sovereignty when it comes to regulating citizenship. These restrictions are placed on the capacity of states to define their own citizens and citizens.

The state's ability to use discretion in citizenship matters is constrained by the universal human rights principle of non-discrimination and the idea that the avoidance of statelessness should be prioritized. A number of international human rights accords acknowledge the basic human right of participation in political and cultural life. This right is a vital component of human rights. These accords begin with the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, which gives the right to participate in government and free elections, the right to engage in the cultural life of the society, the right to peaceful assembly and association, and the right to participate in commerce. Other rights included in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights include the right to participate in trade.

Other international human rights treaties include the African Charter on Human and People's Rights and the European Convention on Human Rights. Both of these treaties were ratified in their respective regions. Participation is not only an essential component of the idea of human rights, but it is also necessary for effective democratic citizenship for every person. As one of its

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fundamental tenets, the Convention on the Rights of the Child acknowledges the significance of children having a voice in decision-making processes. This treaty provides that children, which includes all persons under the age of eighteen, have the right to have their voices heard when adults make choices that impact them, and that appropriate weight should be given to their views in accordance with these decisions. In addition, it specifies that adults should give due consideration to the children's viewpoints in accordance with these decisions.

Dual nationality

It involves contrasting the change in naturalization rates over time for immigrants from Latin American nations that have not modified the legislation with the change in naturalization rates for immigrants from countries that have recently authorized dual citizenship. This comparison was conducted by examining the rates of naturalization of immigrants hailing from Latin American nations that did not alter their legal system. Given the present set of parameters for the model, variations in the regulations governing dual citizenship may be the sole source of systematic change over time in the incentive to naturalize according to nation of origin. For instance, if citizenship is required after welfare reform in order to maintain access to benefits, the effect will primarily be on place of residence (due to the fact that different states have implemented different welfare reform programs) and personal characteristics (such as those provided by the United States welfare system, which are income-tested, categorical (such as education and gender), and which predict eligibility for restricted benefits). For instance, if following welfare reform citizenship is wanted in order to maintain access to benefits, the impact of this decision will rely heavily on the individual's area of residence.

The results provide significant support for the notion that changes in the regulations regulating dual citizenship have led to an increase in the number of persons who have become naturalized citizens. One of the most controversial topics that has arisen in the wake of the passage of the welfare reform law is the question of whether or not immigrants should be encouraged to choose to become citizens rather than in the desire to fully engage in the democratic system of the United States. If this were the case, there would likely be a substantial number of immigrants who choose to become naturalized citizens in order to become eligible for benefits provided by the welfare

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state. Immigrants who already satisfy all of the requirements for naturalization may choose to submit an application for citizenship if they believe that the benefits of becoming a citizen exceed the expenses of doing so. Citizenship offers immigrants access to a variety of political and social privileges that are not available to permanent residents of the country. One of these rights is the ability to vote, which enables immigrants to have a voice in the political decisions that are made and the outcomes that are produced as a consequence of those choices. Having citizenship makes it much simpler to help out family members who came to the country as immigrants. As a direct consequence of the exemption of close relatives of US citizens from immigration quotas, when an immigrant eventually becomes a citizen of the United States, his or her close relatives immediately begin the process of applying for green cards. In addition, a citizen is afforded the option to provide emotional and financial support not just to her spouse and children of any age who are unmarried, but also to her married children of any age, her siblings, and her parents. Since the middle of the 1990s, there has been a general trend toward elevating the significance of citizenry.

Negative Effects at the Psychological Level

It entails comparing the change in naturalization rates over time for immigrants from Latin American nations that have not updated the law with the change in naturalization rates for immigrants from countries that have recently granted dual citizenship. This is done for both groups of immigrants. In order to make this comparison, an examination of the rates of naturalization of immigrants originating from Latin American countries that did not reform their legal system was carried out. Given the current set of parameters for the model, changes in the legislation allowing dual citizenship may be the only source of systematic change over time in the incentive to naturalize according to country of origin. This is the case given the current set of parameters. For example, if citizenship is required in order to maintain access to benefits following the implementation of welfare reform, the effect will primarily be on place of residence (due to the fact that different states have implemented different welfare reform programs) and personal characteristics (such as those provided by the United States welfare system, which are income-tested, categorical (such as education and gender), and which predict eligibility for restricted benefits). For instance, if a person wants to become a citizen as a result of the welfare reform in

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order to continue to receive benefits, the repercussions of this choice will largely be determined by the region in which the individual resides.

The findings provide substantial credence to the hypothesis that changes made to the laws governing dual citizenship are responsible for the observed rise in the number of individuals who have successfully completed the naturalization process and became citizens. The issue of whether or not immigrants should be encouraged to choose to become citizens rather than urged to fully participate in the democratic system of the United States is one of the most contentious subjects that has emerged in the aftermath of the adoption of the welfare reform bill. This question is one of the themes that has caused the greatest controversy since the law was passed. If this were the case, there would certainly be a significant number of immigrants who choose to become naturalized citizens in order to become eligible for benefits offered by the welfare state. These advantages include voting rights and access to health care. If an immigrant believes that the advantages of becoming a citizen outweigh the costs of doing so, they may opt to file an application for citizenship even when they already fulfill all of the conditions for naturalization. This decision is up to the immigrant. Citizenship provides immigrants with access to a number of political and social rights that are not accessible to permanent residents of the nation. These benefits do not include the ability to vote in elections or hold public office. The right to vote is one of these rights, and it gives immigrants a voice in the political decisions that are made and the consequences that are created as a result of the choices that are made. If you are a citizen of the nation, it is considerably easier for you to assist family members who entered the country legally as immigrants. When an immigrant ultimately becomes a citizen of the United States, his or her close relatives immediately begin the process of applying for green cards. This is a direct result of the exemption of close relatives of US citizens from immigration quotas. When an immigrant eventually becomes a citizen of the United States. A citizen also has the ability to offer emotional and financial support not just to her husband and children of any age who are unmarried, but also to her married children of any age, her siblings, and her parents. This is in addition to the ability to aid her spouse and children of any age who are single. There has been a widespread movement, beginning in the middle of the 1990s, toward elevating the relevance of citizenship as an institution.

Conclusion

Previous studies have shown that contextual variables, such as ethnic social networks in the destination country (Liang 1994; Yang 1994), and locals' views towards immigrants (Van Hook, Brown, and Bean), might have an effect on naturalization choices made by immigrants. The criteria of value include those that are decided according to the features of sending nations such as public finance and programmatic assistance (Bloemraad 2006b). Other variables include proximity to the United States of America, economic statistics, and political regimes. (Bueker 2006; Jasso and Rosenzweig 1990; Yang 1994) Among these considerations are governmental money and programmatic assistance for naturalization. The amount of empirical research that have been conducted to investigate the implications of dual citizenship on the naturalization of immigrants is quite few. According to Yang (1994), in the year 1980, immigrants coming from countries that permit dual citizenship had around a 20 percent lower chance of being naturalized compared to immigrants coming from countries that do not permit multiple citizenship. This appears to be in contradiction with the concept that having dual citizenship makes it more probable to become a naturalized citizen. On the other hand, Jones-Correa (2001b) discovered that the rate of naturalization rose in the years following the recognition of dual citizenship for nine Latin American immigrant groups whose nations gave dual citizenship between 1965 and 1997. This was the case for countries that granted dual citizenship between 1965 and 1997. Between 1965 and 1997, these nations engaged in this activity. On the other hand, the identification techniques used in each of these investigations had a number of severe flaws. There is a possibility that the findings of Yang's cross-sectional study are clouded by the existence of features of immigrants' countries of origin that are connected with dual citizenship legislation and also directly influence (unobserved or difficult to assess) newcomers' naturalization preferences. This is due to the fact that these characteristics are linked to regulations governing dual citizenship. On the other hand, the before-and-after approach that was suggested by Jones-Correa can be disguised by the presence of long-term trends in the naturalization rates of immigrants in the United States (for example, in US policy). This enables it to be determined if dual citizenship rights have a causal influence on

the acquisition of citizenship in another nation (and other outcomes) as well as whether or not they have any other effect.

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